

TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER OF REMOTELY PILOTED AIRCRAFT SYSTEMS (RPAS) FOR THE CREATIVE INDUSTRY

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THE INDOOR DRONE FOR CREATIVE INDUSTRIES

Although RPAS offer many creative capacities and advantages, they are not able to be used indoors. This project seeks to develop the world's first indoor RPAS specifically designed for professional use by the Creative Industries.

The main goal is to provide the Creative Industry SMEs with a tool which, by expanding the potential to use different spaces, will help them to offer new services. This in turn will increase their opportunities to grow within the European and international markets.

VALUE PROPOSITION

Designed to meet CIs needs, the RPAS will offer:

- Indoor positioning system
- Movie quality: 4K
- Special shots and takes: 360°, top and below
- Autonomous flying: pre-program adapts to environment
- Safety and security: detect & avoid dynamic & static obstacles

TARGETED CIs

- Advertising
- Architecture
- Fashion
- Movies
- Antiques / Museums
- Music
- Photography
- TV
- Performing Arts
- Arts & Crafts
- Design
- Software
- Video Games